

D7.3 Best Practices Book Waste4Think
WP 4 Creation of Innovative Social Actions
BCNecologia
Public Report – R18.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
EC	European Commission
FA	Food App
ICT / IT	Information and Communication Technologies
MG	Mobile Game
Mx	Number of Month
PAYT	Pay As You Throw
PESA	Cascais Environmental Education and Awareness Program
STEAM	Educational approach to learning that uses Science, Technology, Engineering, the Arts and Mathematics
W2S	Waste 2 Sort game
W4T	WASTE4THINK Moving towards Life Cycle Thinking by integrating Advanced Waste Management Systems
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

In accordance with the Waste4Think Grant Agreement, this "Book of Good Practices" includes the best initiatives found in the four municipalities in which Pay As You Throw schemes and other actions have been implemented.

The aim of this manual is to compile and transfer the best waste management solutions tested by the four pilots, so that these experiences can be replicated in other municipalities. Therefore, this document is presented in such a way that it can be used as an inspiring catalog.

This deliverable has a close relationship with many other tasks and deliverables foreseen by other Work Packages, in particular:

- D1.2 “Best Practices database in Circular Economy, Economic Instruments and Prevention Actions WP1 Pilots planning and execution” which collects, in accordance with the definitions and regulations in the Annex I of the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, the best initiatives found in the European Union related to circular economy actions, economic instruments used, focusing on PAYT, and prevention actions related to waste management.
- D4.1 “Implementation of R17: non ICT Innovative Social Actions WP 4 Creation of Innovative Social Actions”. - Public Report M12. This deliverable describes the environmental education strategies to be followed during the implementation of each pilot, including the most innovative social actions to reach a high level of awareness and change in habits from the different targets involved. One of the objectives of Waste4Think is to develop best environmental education and awareness strategies and to present it along with the implementation of all the required actions to undertake the demonstrative objectives of the Pilots sites. The final goal is to reach a high rate of empowerment and awareness and finally, a change in consumption and waste management habits among the different stakeholders involved in the implementation of the different actions.
- D4.2. “Implementation of R17: ICT based Innovative Social Actions”. – Public Report M18 This report includes the forecast of the availability and use in the Environmental Educational Strategy, of the ICT based tools developed in the framework of the Waste4Think project.

Within the framework of Waste4Think, a total of 86 actions have been developed over the years with more than 170 related implementations. This book includes 21 actions that have been catalogued as Good Practices by the technicians of each Pilot, together with the Urban Ecology Agency of Barcelona (BCNecologia) for their replicability and their social, economic and environmental impact.

The description of the Good Practices will include formal tables for each good practice option with objectives, methodology, expected and actual results, recommendations and contact person(s).

2 Content and methodology

2.1 Main Selection of Best Practices

The selection of the best practices has been accorded between the responsible of the Pilots and the coordinator of this document, BCNecologia. To be considered "best practices", the different pilots had to be able to testify through qualitative and quantitative indicators that they achieved, directly or indirectly, progress in terms of awareness, prevention, circularity and development of related economic instruments. At the same time, all the Practices are related to the Waste Hierarchy determined by the EU.

The 21 actions selected are the following:

Seveso:

- Lunch/Dinner with Waste.
- Virtuous Households Separated Collection Contest.
- Virtuous Households Prevention Waste Contest.
- Celebration and Monitoring Ecoevents.
- Implementation of the PAYT System in Seveso

Cascais:

- Door to door Campaign.
- Gamification Awards Systems.
- Green Contacts (Door to Door Support).
- PESA Cascais Ambiente.

Zamudio:

- Mapping waste collection facilities, households and local economic activities.
- Campaign for the educational centers using different kind of learning materials.
- Introduction of a self-composting in the schools.
- Creative cooking course.
- Food redistribution with remains of food between poor families.
- Tupper and reusable campaign.
- Citizens participation process to introduce PAYT and discuss with citizens the new tax associated.
- Distribution of menstrual cups.
- Euskal ecounter competition.

Halandri:

- Environmental program in vocational schools.
- Use of Ecodesign Game.
- Biowaste separate collection implementation.

2.2 Type of Best Practices

All W4T Good Practices have one thing in common: the intention to raise awareness and educate about waste and how to avoid the impacts associated with its mismanagement, promoting good citizen habits from the consumption of goods, management at origin, co-responsibility in the separation, and other.

Although these good practices can be highlighted for their transversality given that their impact can be recognized in more than one step of the waste hierarchy, we have divided them into three large groups.

- Practices focused on waste prevention:

- Lunch - Dinner with Waste (Seveso)
- Celebration and Monitoring Ecoevents (Seveso).
- Gamification Award System. (Cascais)
- Green Contacts (Door to door support). (Cascais)
- Food redistribution with remains of food between poor families (Zamudio).
- Creative Cooking Course (Zamudio).
- Reusable tupper and bag campaign (Zamudio).

It is interesting to note that, of all these good practices, there is a large majority aimed at the prevention of food waste, which is consistent given that the four pilot municipalities are located in southern Europe, where the management of this type of waste is more complex and less developed.

- Practices focused on improving the separate collection of waste, including those aimed at promoting PAYT:

- Mapping Waste Collection Facilities, Household and Local Economic Activities (Zamudio).
- Citizen Participation process to introduce PAYT and discuss with citizens the new tax associated (Zamudio).
- Implementation of the PAYT system in Seveso.
- Virtuous Households Separated Collection Contest. (Seveso)
- Introduction of a self-composting in the schools (Zamudio)
- Door to door campaign (Cascais).
- Biowaste separate collection implementation. (Halandri).

In this group of Good Practices, it is important to point out the important effort that it has meant for the municipalities to mobilize time and work resources side by side with the citizens. However, it is also the most effective way of making citizens co-responsible for the municipal burden in terms of resources allocated to waste collection services, ensuring that information arrives and knowing first-hand the doubts and questions that people have about this matter. From this point of view, they are also instruments for better governance.

- Awareness-raising in schools and other learning communities:

- Campaign in educational institutions. (Zamudio).

- Euskal Ecounter Competition. (Zamudio)
- PESA Cascais Ambiente. (Cascais)
- Use of Ecodesign Game (Halandri).
- Environmental program in Vocational schools (Halandri).

As for the Best Practices aimed at student communities, there are two main target groups: primary and secondary school students on the one hand, and university students on the other.

In the primary and secondary group, it is necessary to point out the necessary complicity with an educational community that must be motivated because they already assume a lot of workload due to the demands of the educational system itself. In this sense, it is worth highlighting the differential of those teachers who are especially involved because they consider environmental issues to be a priority.

With regard to the Best Practices aimed at university students, it should be pointed out that the use of digital games is a powerful tool for disseminating the principles and solutions of circular economy. When they have been used in environments where students are not particularly linked to environmental issues in their curricular profile, they are surprised by the number of options that exist for improving sustainability. Therefore, we understand that these games can be a tool to consider as dissemination of environmental solutions in other environments of university meetings in key videogames.

3 Waste4Think Best Practices

This section presents the Best Practices, one by one, in the form of a table.

3.1 Seveso

LUNCH/DINNER WITH WASTE			
ID	SE.1		
Municipality or Area	Seveso		
Basic data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Country: Seveso, Lombardy, Italy - Population: 21.870 - Period of implementation: from 2017 to 2018 - Current status: Finished - Language(s): English 		
Description of the case study	<p>The municipality of Seveso organized, in conjunction with the citizens, a total of 4 self-organized dinners in which the facilitators explained how to give value to food waste. The 4 dinners were made in different parts of the city; one in the street, 2 in a Public Room and the last one, in an urban garden (public space). The interest of these dinners was learning about to put in value food waste, sharing tableware creating more sense of community.</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign <input type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	Waste fraction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Collection <input type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> On site treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	Waste management stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies
Communication tools	Leaflet, "social street" approach.		
Training tools	Stand with roll up. Sorting game, Questionnaire to check the attitude about separate collection and prevention. Sample of bags and containers.		

N. of stakeholders involved (expected and effective)	<p>They predicted 150 participants and finally attended 125 citizens.</p>	
Rate of participation (% or number)	<p>80-87%</p>	
Key points of success	<p>On the street / indoor in some public spaces.</p>	
Social economical impact / benefit (forecasted and/or achieved, please specify)	<p>Use of food waste and Use of reusing tableware</p>	
Costs related	<p>Each dinner has a cost of 8 person-hours and € 120 per facilitator.</p>	
Quality of the information found related to replicability of the campaign	<p>Methodology applicable in other municipalities or neighborhoods with a target group of about 50 people. Highly recommended to introduce at parties or local fairs.</p>	
Information source	<p>Waste4Think</p>	
Link to the specific case study	<p>https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/SEVESO/strategies/9</p>	
Further information (contact, organization)	<p>AgenziaInnova 21- Seveso City Council- info@agenziainnova21.org agenziainnova21@itpec.it</p>	

VIRTUOUS HOUSEHOLDS SEPARATED COLLECTION CONTEST			
ID	SE.2		
Municipality or Area	Seveso		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Seveso, Lombardy, Italy</p> <p>- Population: 21.870</p> <p>- Period of implementation: from 04/2018 to 11/2018</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Description of the case study	<p>The action aims to select a small number of households(8), monitoring very strictly and continuously training them to improve their separated collection. These households receive a training and are be part of a prize so that those with the highest recycling rate will be awarded. The monitoring of the waste production is done individually by the families themselves with the help of a monitoring kit (i.e. dynamometer, eco-bags, registry), during the trial (one month), in order to verify the range of improvement. Furthermore, a characterization of residual waste will be done by technicians for the selected households. Also, some weighting (at least) in two times (before and after the action) will be done by technicians for the whole building hosting the selected households, to compare their results with the average of the building.</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	<p>Type of campaign</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Glass</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Food waste</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Clothes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> All packaging</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other _____</p>	<p>Waste fraction</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Prevention</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Redesign</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Reuse</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collection</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Recycling</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Treatment</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> On site treatment</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other _____</p>	<p>Waste management stage</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Citizen</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Students</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> SME</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Researchers</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Associations</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generato</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies</p>
Communication	- Municipal web site, Facebook and Twitter, leaflet to promote the event.		
Tools	- Families were recruited by a public tender published on municipal website. Since the deadline for applying was too short, some families have been directly		

	contacted by municipality and by ARS staff (partner in Seveso).
Training tools	A starting meeting with recruited family had the scope to train them for the weighting and registering activity.
N. of stakeholders involved (expected and effective)	Expected: 10 households. Effective: 8 households
Rate of participation (% or number)	80%
Key points of success	Lessons learned: Conviviality and user-friendliness.
Quantitative targets	The maximum level of separate collection in the families reached 95% and the per capita unsorted waste production about 5-10 kg/inhabitant year, much lower than the current Seveso average. This means that, despite the very high level already reached by Seveso citizens, there is still room for improvement. Training of the families would have been more consistent (for instance with some written guidelines or periodic visits).
Environmental impact	The peer-to-peer event, where families are protagonist, could be particularly meaningful to improve the collective awareness on waste management improving the environment.
Social economical impact / benefit (forecasted and/or achieved, please specify)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The peer-to-peer event, where families are protagonist, could be particularly meaningful to improve the collective consciousness on waste management. - No significant economic impact.

Costs related	<p><u>Citizens involvement phase</u>: External cost -> Cost for activating the telephone number = 60 euro Staff -> Cost for young person in charge of following the action and giving technical support = 500 euro (for all the period)</p> <p><u>Training and monitoring period</u>: Implementation cost -> 8 dynamometers for families = 80 € Implementation cost -> 8 gift cards to be spent by awarded families at “La Botanica” shop and restaurant in Seveso = 800 euro Staff -> Cost for young person in charge of following the action and giving technical support = 500 euro (for all the period, comprehensive of the recruiting phase).</p> <p><u>Feedback activities</u>: Implementation cost for communication items: - 30 posters = 150 € - 1000 leaflets (A5, coloured) = 110 € - Graphics designer = 700 € TOTAL = 960 €</p>
Monitoring methodology	The data collected during the activity was the data used for the feedback towards citizens and towards the municipality. All the data published are anonymous.
Quality of the information found related to replicability of the campaign	Methodology applicable in other municipalities or neighborhoods who can assume the following of all the process of the project with the 3 phases.
Information source	Waste4Think
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/SEVESO/strategies/10
Further information (contact, organization)	AgenziaInnova 21- Seveso City Council- info@agenziainnova21.org agenziainnova21@itpec.it

VIRTUOUS HOUSEHOLDS PREVENTION WASTE CONTEST			
ID	SE2.4		
Municipality or Area	Seveso		
Basic data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Country: Seveso, Lombardy, Italy - Population: 21.870 - Period of implementation: from 05/2019to 10/2019 - Current status: Finished - Language(s): English 		
Description of the case study	<p>"The Virtuous Households 2.0 focused on ""Free Waste Families"", willing to reduce waste production as much as possible. Families must have good waste management at heart and be available either to attend a training meeting or to receive visits or phone calls from the project's technicians.</p> <p>The handbook of waste reduction actions for families' inspiration is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drink tap water - Buy bulk foods in reusable nets or containers - Use reusable shopping bags - Use handkerchiefs and washable napkins - Use washable tableware - Use washable crockery, even for picnics and homemade parties - Give presents made of experiences, not packaging - To clean, use vinegar and baking soda, which are better than many chemicals - Use washable baby diapers instead of disposable ones - Do not waste food and reduce food surpluses" 		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____ 	Waste fraction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Collection <input type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> On site treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____ 	Waste management stage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generato <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies

Communication Tools	<p>- Municipal and W4T websites and local press; activation of a specific telephone number to call for subscribing to the action and asking questions during it; activation of a specific email address for supporting the action (famiglievirtuose@arsambiente.it); WhatsApp Group; Facebook and Twitter posts.</p>
Training tools	<p>WhatsApp group landed by ARS with recruited families to start and follow the action, answering for questions, doubts, etc. Guidelines for the families participating.</p>
Other tools developed during the campaign	<p>Municipal Official Decision n. 48 of 4/4/2019 and related disciplinary describing the action.</p>
N. of stakeholders involved (expected and effective)	<p>Expected: 10 households. Effective: 7 households</p>
Rate of participation (% or number)	<p>70%</p>
Key points of success	<p>The action was carried out during municipal elections. In order to avoid political interferences (e.g. news blackout) and to have the whole availability of the municipal staff it would have been better to implement it in another period.</p> <p>Peer-to-peer event</p>
Costs related	<p><u>Recruiting phase:</u> - 840 euro for the final awards for each family</p> <p>- 145 euro for 29 water bottles, one for each families' member</p> <p><u>Training and monitoring period and results phase:</u> Implementation cost -> Staff internal cost = 20 man-days</p> <p>Gift vouchers = 840 euro</p>
Monitoring methodology	<p>Each family is in charge to self-monitor its waste every week, filling a personal Google doc.</p>
Quality of the information found related to replicability of the campaign	<p>Methodology applicable in other municipalities or neighborhoods who can assume the following of all the process of the project.</p>

Information source	Waste4Think
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/SEVESO/actions/84
Further information (contact, organization)	AgenziaInnova 21- Seveso City Council- info@agenziainnova21.org agenziainnova21@itpec.it

CELEBRATION AND MONITORING ECOEVENTS			
ID	SE3		
Municipality or Area	Seveso		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Seveso, Lombardy, Italy</p> <p>- Population: 21.870</p> <p>- Period of implementation: from 2017 to 2019.</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Description of the case study	<p>In the Bosco delle Querce area, in Seveso, during the summer, there are a lot of events. The bigger ones have around 3.000 participants for every lunch and dinner. Without the proper planning, huge amounts of catering and lightweight packaging waste are generated during the events. Those Eco-events have had two phases:</p> <p>Seveso, setting up a new regulation, has defined criteria for a specific number of events to have been organized there or in other places of the city. Seveso Municipality has purchased the necessary equipment to support these eco-events, specifically aiming at using washable catering, also economically supporting the Associations in order to manage dishwasher, etc. The Associations, implementing Eco-events, have obtained a reduced waste fee.</p> <p>2ond phase: Celebration and monitoring of the Ecoevents. These events have been monitored by calculating indicators (overall waste produced and separated composition of waste, etc.), that are related to the environmental impact, comparing to the other events where no zero waste practices have been implemented. In relation of these events, there has been some activities of sensitization and information to the citizens and associations which have been organizing events in Seveso area.</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign	Waste fraction	Waste management stage
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other_____	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Collection <input type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> On site treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: Separate Collection	<input type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants

			<i>Operators</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>Waste Manager Public Bodies</i>
Communication Tools	- Municipal website, paper advertisement (placemat), twitter and facebook, local (web)newspapers		
Training tools	Before the event, the organizing association has been trained by ARS on eco-events organization aspects. Just before the event, all the volunteers, involved in the event management, have been trained on separate collection by ARS and SEVESO municipality.		
Other tools developed during the campaign	Municipal Official Decision n. 48 of 4/4/2019 and related disciplinary describing the action.		
N. of stakeholders involved (expected and effective)	Expected: 30.000. Effective: 32.890		
Key points of success	<p>Good commitment of organizing association, volunteers training, presence of public authority (Seveso's Major), sensitization action in support by Legambiente, increase of the number of eco-events over time.</p> <p>Associations organizing eco-events, especially for the first time, have to be adequately trained and motivated. Even if they could raise some doubts or see only obstacles, the good results of the past events, also in terms of economic and social benefits, usually convince them. In addition, participants have to be sensitized especially on the environmental meaning of the event, in order to let them to change their habits also at home. Every season the purchase of equipment is fine-tuned according to the past experience.</p>		
Quantitative targets	<p>Rate of separate collection 95,7%</p> <p>Quantity collected of light packaging per capita 29,57g/ capita.</p> <p>Number of Eco-events 45</p> <p>Global cost for setting up and organizing Eco-events during the project: 35.000€</p> <p>Number of attendees or participants: 32.890.</p>		
Environmental impact	In the eco-events, the separate collection rate is significantly higher than in the normal events and also waste generation is reduced to a minimum. This results in a lower environmental impact. The action promotes also a change of habits at home with an indirect positive effect on waste management and its impact. The environmental impact of using ceramic dishes and a local dishwasher, in terms of energy consumption and CO2 production, is lower than single use plastic if at least 30 eco-events are organized.		

<p>Social economical impact / benefit</p>	<p>The action promotes a change of habits at home. From surveys performed in some of the eco-events, citizens are happy to use washable tableware because of the zero-waste production and also because of the feeling of eating in a restaurant.</p> <p>Associations organizing events also changed their attitude over time, being more positive committed in organizing different kind of events in the future.</p> <p>The economic impact was also positive because associations organizing the event saved money for: better management of waste, avoided purchasing of disposable cutlery and dishes, better comfort of participants with a greater success (not quantifiable).</p>
<p>Costs related</p>	<p>Specific costs of the implementation activity paid by the Seveso Municipality through the project funds:</p> <p>-> Tableware</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Arcopal plane plates N. 2600 Cost: € 2.321 - Arcopal dessert plane plates: N. 1000 Cost: € 954 - Poly-carbonate glasses: N. 2000 Cost: € 1.209 <p>Moreover, the ASD Association purchased 3000 metal cutlery (about 600 €). The total cost for the social cooperative in charge of waste management assistance and weighing was 15.000 euro.</p> <p><u>Total costs</u> (2017+2018+2019): 35.000 €, Number of Meals (2017+2018): 32.890, Specific cost: 1,064€/meal.</p> <p>Savings thanks to avoided purchase of disposable cutlery and dishes (estimated): 0,35 €/meal</p>
<p>Monitoring methodology</p>	<p>For all the events organized in the months of August and September 2017 in Seveso, ARS with the collaboration of the municipality set up a monitoring system based on a detailed reporting on: number of participants (KPI), waste</p>

	<p>management (separate collection, frequent mistakes, etc.) and waste weighing, allowing to calculate the rate of selective collection reached in each event (KPI). Especially for some of the Eco-events, it was conducted a social survey with the means of a “smile-totem” in order to collect the participants’ feelings (social acceptance – KPI).</p> <p>Also in 2018, the monitoring foresaw the same activities and the monitoring of the energy consumptions of the dish-washer.</p>
Quality of the information found related to replicability of the campaign	<p>The new regulation and the results obtained by the Municipality of Seveso defining specific criteria for the management of the tent for summer events, in order to reach environmental and social objectives can be an inspiration for other municipalities to reach the same goals for another eco-events.</p> <p>See the new regulation in the tender: https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/media/implementations/documents/SAI42_Bando_Te ndostruttura_Seveso_Det_Nr_138_del_22_3_17.pdf</p>
Information source	Waste4Think
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/SEVESO/actions/84
Further information (contact, organization)	<p>AgenziaInnova 21- Seveso City Council- info@agenziainnova21.org</p> <p>agenziainnova21@itpec.it</p>

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PAYT SYSTEM IN SEVESO			
ID	SE4		
Municipality or Area	Seveso		
Basic data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Country: Seveso, Lombardy, Italy - Population: 21.870 - Period of implementation: from 04/2017 to 11/2019. - Current status: Finished - Language(s): English 		
Description of the case study	<p>After the approval of the local regulation by the City Council, starting from 1° May 17, the blue bags with RFID started to be counted in order to introduce PAYT in Seveso. The payment of the collecting waste fee has been divided in two parts: a fixed fee, payed in May (90% of the total amount), and a variable fee in November, calculated for each user on the basis of the number of bags collected by <i>Gelsia Ambiente</i> from May to October. In this way, the cost of each bag is equal to 2,30 €.</p> <p>The implementation PAYT had different phases.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PAYT regulation approval. - Public Information event citizen. - Information letter on PAYT in public space. - Questionnaire on PAYT in public spaces. - Information letters on PAYT for zero-users. - Final Survey on PAYT in public spaces. 		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign	Waste fraction	Waste management stage
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Collection <input type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> On site treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: Separate Collection	<input type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generato <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies

<p>Communication</p> <p>Tools</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Letter to all households: 9.000 - Letter to zero-waste users: almost 2.000 - Open public meeting for citizens - Press conference for media - Websites (Municipal and W4T websites) - Social media (facebook, twitter) - Press release and newspaper - Funny Door to door campaign (see also SE1) - The fixed part of the invoice sent to all the users, contained also an official letter, informing the citizens about the new way of charging the waste tax. - Furthermore, the citizens have been informed during an evening public meeting (12th of April 2017), through social network and websites (official Seveso Municipality website and Facebook pages). - Media have been informed through a press-conference on the same day of the public event (12th of April 2017). They wrote some news in their newspaper in the following days. <p>Furthermore, an official letter has been sent in October 2017 to the zero-waste users (almost 2.000). They're users that didn't deliver any blue bag during the year. The zero-waste users have to justify the zero-waste production to the municipality, otherwise they will be charged with a rate, based on the average blue bag collection.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It's necessary to fight against the phenomenon of zero-waste production, because frequently it hides illegal behaviors (i.e. illegal waste dumping, not proper use of ibags, etc.).
<p>Training tools</p>	<p>Public officers, working in Seveso Municipality, have been informed and trained by ARS and Softline people about PAYT, and its technical features in order to be able to answer to citizens' complaints and questions.</p> <p>The draft of the regulation has been carefully explained to members of municipal council by ARS people in order to let them understand its main contents.</p>
<p>Other tools developed during the campaign</p>	<p>In August 2017, the Municipality, together with GELSIA, the waste management company, introduced the orange bag for families with newborns or invalid or ill people needing diapers. The orange bag is collected in the same days of the blue one but does not enter in the calculation of the variable part of the waste tax.</p> <p>Furthermore, it is provided for the next months the introduction by Softline of a citizens' app linked to the municipal database allowing citizens to know more about separate collection (day of collections, ways to sort, etc.) and to be daily updated on their waste production.</p>
<p>Rate of participation (% or number)</p>	<p>75-100% depending on the phase of the implementation</p>

<p>Key points of success</p>	<p>Seveso has successfully introduced the PAYT thanks to the introduction, some years ago, of the ibag. The experimentation with ibag before the tax is a key element because: citizens could gradually change their habits and understand the meaning of less waste production and how to sort correctly their waste; and the waste management company together with the municipality can solve the technical issues related to technological aspects (malfunction of RFID or sensors, wrong assignment of the bag to the user, etc.) before the introduction of the new charging system.</p> <p>The sensitization activities have a key role to help all the targets involved in understand the change.</p> <p>Furthermore, the political commitment has been necessary to approve the new regulation, despite internal oppositions.</p> <p>To be successful is needed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Political commitment - Officers' training - Sensitization actions tailored to the specific targets involved - Specific treatments for special needs (e.g. diapers, etc.) - Illegal behaviors controls
<p>Environmental impact</p>	<p>Environmental impact avoided thank to the less production of waste, more well-being and economic savings.</p>
<p>Social economical impact/benefit</p>	<p>PAYT is a more equal system to charge citizens on the bases of their real behavior in waste production and sorting. So, it's a way to introduce equity. Another impact comes from the environmental impact avoided thank to the less production of waste, because it contributes in well-being and economic savings.</p> <p>The economic impact is consequent to "equity" and could be positive if the user is committed to produce less waste, also changing its purchasing habits, or negative if the user produces more unsorted waste than the average.</p> <p>The economic impact could be positive also for the municipality that could have significant global savings thank to the less waste dumping and more incomes from separated fractions.</p>
<p>Costs related</p>	<p><u>Costs to carry out regulation:</u></p> <p>Personnel cost (ARS, SEVESO, Softline): 20 days/man</p>

	<p>1.000 € for letter to citizens (+ 4.000 € already covered by the tax)</p> <p>1.500 € for letter to zero waste users</p> <p>15.000 €/year for double invoicing</p> <p>Other expenditures are already covered by the service charge due to the waste management company (GELSIA), by the W4T funding and by the tax paid by citizens (e.g. 60.000 €/year for blue bags with RFID are already covered).</p>
Monitoring methodology	<p>Data on waste collection (separate collection rate, weight of all the fractions, number of bags, zero-waste producers, etc.) and PAYT payments are regularly collected by municipality and waste management company in their databases. This data is available for W4T monitoring.</p> <p>A first questionnaire has been submitted to a group of citizens (about 100) in summer 2017, in order to verify their social acceptance of the new tax.</p> <p>Those ones regarding social acceptance could be estimated through specific questionnaire. The purpose is to repeat the questionnaire periodically (each year) in order to verify the social acceptance from a high number of citizens.</p>
Quality of the information found related to replicability of the campaign	<p>The new regulation and the results obtained by the Municipality of Seveso defining specific criteria for the PAYT can be an inspiration for other municipalities to reach the same goals for other eco-events.</p> <p>See the new regulation in this link: https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/media/implementations/documents/SAI91_PAYT_regulation_extract_from_D5.3.pdf</p>
Information source	Waste4Think
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/SEVESO/strategies/11
Further information (contact, organization)	<p>AgenziaInnova 21- Seveso City Council- info@agenziainnova21.org</p> <p>agenziainnova21@itpec.it</p>

3.2 Cascais

DOOR TO DOOR CAMPAIGN			
ID	C1		
Municipality or Area	Cascais		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Cascais, Lisboa, Portugal</p> <p>- Population: 174,000</p> <p>- Period of implementation: from 2018 to 2019</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Description of the case study	<p>The main goal of this action is to engage citizens in the target area in the project as participants and beneficiaries of the project. For this to be achieved, we have designed a method that merges the contact stages, namely the inquiry (which requires over 10 minutes) the registration and bins use explanation. This ensures a continuous and friendly dialogue with the citizens and even if some are not willing to participate, at least their opinion is registered in the inquiry. We consider the target area as a whole.</p> <p>The campaign was made in 2 phases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct contact with potential participants (target audience) to present the project and its benefits. Register the participants. - Green contact: To engage participants and have a continuous relationship (proximity) <p>Staff members will go door to door to give some useful utensils to participants.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Utensils (eco bags for recycling, reusable fruit bags, to be defined) 		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign	Waste fraction	Waste management stage
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Collection <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Onsite treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies

Waste fraction	All waste
Communication tools	Direct contact with own staff comprised by six full time monitors.
Training tools	Flyer, biowaste bags and access key. This key is an NFC tag that allows to extract usage information of each household. It registers who, when and where it was used and with this information, we can calculate points given and expected gain of recycling rate.
N. of stakeholders involved (expected and effective)	Expected: 500 households Effective: 500 households
Rate of participation (% or number)	100%
Key points of success	<p>Direct contact and conversation to explain issues.</p> <p>Direct contact will surpass multiple questions or doubts from participants. It will increase confidence between stakeholders.</p>
Environmental impact	For the first six months of the project, recycling rate has increased from 11% to 28%.
Social economical impact / benefit (forecasted and/or achieved, please specify)	<p>Over 507 registrations. This will allow for a full project participation and to collect all benefits from that. Not only the city points given, but also offers from the management (eco theme related) and information about the waste each household produces.</p> <p>Citizens were really interested in the eco-bags and they saw this approach as a great tool for awareness.</p>
Costs related	<p>1st phase: The cost was around €5 000 as it was the cost for the young marketers which went door to door during the activity.</p> <p>2nd phase: 5 000€ related to communication staff (monitors to engage in direct contact with citizens)</p>
Monitoring methodology	Surveys and registration account where all information will solely be used to identify bin usage and waste production patterns according to the project's goals.
Quality of the information found related to replicability of the	<p>The implementations of a new waste management system generate doubts in the citizen and it is also a challenge of habits changes.</p> <p>The direct contact with the citizens permits to identify those doubts and clarify</p>

campaign	<p>them and also to take into account some problematic that was not thought of in the planning.</p> <p>This is a way to create confidence between the public service of waste management and citizens.</p>
Information source	Cascais - EMAC
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/CASCAIS/strategies/20

GAMMIFICATION AWARDS SYSTEM			
ID	C1.4.		
Municipality or Area	Cascais		
Basic data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Country: Cascais, Lisboa, Portugal - Population: 174,000 - Period of implementation: from 205 to 2019 - Current status: - Language(s): English 		
Description of the case study	<p>This action aims to create interactive gratification and accumulation of points that can be deducted in a number of services, for families and other participants of the Pay As You Throw project. The model for system:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -One key usage per day provides 1 point -Over 22 of usage per month: bonus 5 points -Collective performance improving: bonus 10 points -The information is shared in a shadow invoice (eco-performance) -Automated monthly of points assessment through in-house programming. - This action also aims to increase awareness to ecological issues and ways in which they can help. 		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign	Waste fraction	Waste management stage
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other_____	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Collection <input type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Onsite treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centers <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies
Waste fraction	Glass, light, packaging, residual waste, paper and cardboard.		
Communication	Direct contact with own staff comprised by six full time monitors.		

tools	Facebook and Instagram Cascais Ambiente official pages.
Training tools	Flyer, biowaste bags and access key. This key is an NFC tag that allows to extract usage information of each household. It registers who, when and where it was used and with this information, we can calculate points given and expected gain of recycling rate.
N. of stakeholders involved (expected and effective)	Expected: 500 households Effective: 300 households
Rate of participation (% or number)	60%
Key points of success	Easy usage of app is determinant for the success of these gamification instruments. - social media login facilitates the process - Multilanguage is better
Environmental impact	Increase of recycling levels 11% to 28%.
Social economical impact / benefit (forecasted and/or achieved, please specify)	Over 300 monthly regular users of the App.
Costs related	The cost of the app ascends 50 000 Euros, but the integration of the gamification process can be programmed as an "add on" making it cheaper. The cost of keys is around 2 000 Euros for the pilot area
Monitoring methodology	The system directly uploads information on bin usage as the key is introduced into the handle at each recycling bin. This facilitates any statistical analysis on the project's progress, more specifically, information on its Social and Economical Impacts. There should also be handed out a survey at the end of each semester (for example) to get an overview of its success and collect information to quantify Social Impact.
Information source	Cascais – EMAC (Municipal Environment Company of Cascais)
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/CASCAIS/implementations/168

GREEN CONTACTS (DOOR TO DOOR SUPORT)			
ID	C1.6		
Municipality or Area	Cascais		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Cascais, Lisboa, Portugal</p> <p>- Population: 174,000</p> <p>- Period of implementation: from 12/2018 to 10/2019</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Description of the case study	<p>To engage participants and have a continuous relationship (proximity) Staff members will go door to door to give some useful utensils to participants. Utensils are: eco bags for recycling, reusable fruit bags, and others.</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	Waste fraction <input type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Collection <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Onsite treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	Waste management stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centers <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Residential flat buildings and other households <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies
Waste fraction	Glass Light packaging Paper and cardboard Residual waste		
Communication tools	Direct contact with own staff comprised by six full time monitors. Facebook and Instagram Cascais Ambiente official pages		
Training tools	Flyer, biowaste bags and access key. This key is an NFC tag that allows to extract usage information of each household. It registers who, when and where it was used and with this information, we can calculate points given and expected gain of recycling rate.		
N. of stakeholders involved (expected and effective)	520 households		
Rate of participation (% or number)	100%		
Key points of success			

	Direct contact with households. Personal contact is useful as you understand the user's profile.
Costs related	€5 000 related to communication staff, monitors to engage in direct contact with citizens.
Monitoring methodology	Number of households directly contacted
Information source	Waste4Think
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/CASCAIS/implementations/47
Further information	Cascais Ambiente https://ambiente.cascais.pt/

PESA CASCAIS AMBIENTE			
ID	C.3.3		
Municipality or Area	Cascais		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Cascais, Lisboa, Portugal</p> <p>- Population: 174,000</p> <p>- Period of implementation: from 01/2019 to 06/2019</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Description of the case study	<p>Over 80 projects are currently available as part of another ongoing project called PESA- for schools and teachers to enroll. The issues of waste reduction, separation, recycling, consumption, civic behaviours that contribute to a sustainable development and an ecological footprint analysis and ways to reduce it, are in at least 18 separate activities, covering students from the 1st grade all the way up to the senior year of high school.</p> <p>The idea is to integrate and promote W4T in every activity as much as possible and introduce posters around the schools, promoting the gaming apps.</p> <p>Specifically:</p> <p>In-Class activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Good Eco-friendly behaviours"- 1st graders • "Let's help the planet!"- 1st-4th graders • "Recycling means changing"- 3rd graders • "The pathway of our waste" - 7th to 9th graders • "Organic farming and healthy living" - 5th to 12th graders • "Climate Change: causes and effects" - 7th to 9th graders • "Waste in promoting Circular Economy" - 10th to 12th graders (high school) • "Climate change and our Oceans" – High school <p>Outdoor activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Organic farms in the schools" - all years • "Composting in School" - all years • "Schools resilience to Climate Change"- 7th to 12th graders • "Nature Conservation activities" - 3rd to 12th graders • "Sustainable Development Goals" - 7th to 12th graders • "Giving life to Garbage" - 2nd graders 		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign	Waste fraction	Waste management stage
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Collection Recycling	<input type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations

	<input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> On site treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Residential flat buildings and other households <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies
Waste fraction	All waste		
Communication tools	Direct contact with own staff comprised by six full time monitors. Facebook and Instagram Cascais Ambiente official pages		
Training tools	Education presentations and W4T apps Promotional Video		
Other tools developed during the campaign	Educational department presentations with w4t lettering and logos 		
N. of stakeholders involved	Expected: 350 Effective: 500		
Rate of participation (% or number)	142%		
Key points of success	Engage students with Apps, it is a different approach for them from ordinary classes.		
Environmental impact	This is always a difficult point to measure. In this case the best way is by analyzing the adherence to W4T projects such as PAYT, and the uploading of the available apps.		
Social economical impact/benefit	Engages students in the w4t project discussion, create "buzz".		
Monitoring methodology	Accounting for number of activities and students engaged. A survey is handed out after each activity by the staff to the present teacher,		

	and afterwards the information is uploaded onto the PESA database. The best way is for this survey to be filled along with the students so they give out their own input of the relevance of the activity, the information given and whether or not they retrieved a lot of new ideas and civic behaviors.
Information source	Waste4Think
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/CASCAIS/implementations/169
Further information	Cascais Municipality

3.3 Zamudio

MAPPING WASTE COLLECTION FACILITIES, HOUSEHOLDS AND LOCAL ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES			
ID	Z1.3		
Municipality or Area	Zamudio		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Zamudio, Basque Country, Spain</p> <p>- Population: 21.870</p> <p>- Period of implementation: from 2017-05-02 to 2017-05-19</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Why it has been identified as a best practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Innovative methodology and digitalization of data in in Open Source Platform 		
Description of the case study	<p>This activity of Citizen Science in the municipality of Zamudio has a main objective the realization "in situ" of an inventory of services, activities, facilities and other elements of the municipal scope, being carried out subsequently a process of digitalization and topological validation of the collected information.</p> <p>The geographical elements listed in a table have been incorporated into the <i>Open Street Map</i> platform, so that the digital information generated can be shared and edited by other users. In addition, the DeustoTech Energy team has developed 3D visualizations with the data obtained.</p> <p>This geographic information served as the basis for subsequent studies and analysis on waste management, as well as designing environmental awareness and awareness campaigns.</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign	Waste fraction	Waste management stage
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collection <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> On site treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants

			<i>Operators</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>Waste Manager Public Bodies</i>
Waste fraction	Municipal and Commercial Wastes		
Communication tools	Print Maps and 3D Maps		
Other tools developed	Action-research methodology employed		
N. of stakeholders involved (expected and effective)	Expected: 20 citizens Effective: 18		
Rate of participation (% or number)	90%		
Key points of success	High rate of participation.		
Social economical impact / benefit (forecasted and/or achieved, please specify)	The location of the key points of Zamudio of waste collection has allowed having a direct contact with the citizens and the main economic activities to develop the next steps of the development of PAYT and a direct contact to involve the citizens in the project.		
Costs related	Print maps: 10 €		
Monitoring methodology	Those ones regarding social acceptance could be estimated through specific questionnaire. The purpose is to repeat the questionnaire periodically (each year) in order to verify the social acceptance from a high number of citizens.		
Quality of the information found related to replicability of the campaign	Replicable methodology in other municipalities or neighborhoods with up to 5,000 inhabitants.		
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/ZAMUDIO/implementations/97		
Further information (contact, organization)	https://energia.deusto.es/demos/materials/		

CAMPAIGN FOR THE EDUCATIONAL CENTERS USING DIFFERENT KIND OF LEARNING AND MATERIALS			
ID	Z2.1		
Municipality or Area	Zamudio		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Zamudio, Basque Country, Spain</p> <p>- Population: 21.870</p> <p>- Period of implementation: from 2016 to 2019.</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Why it has been identified as a best practice	The amount of participators and the quality of the dissemination of the zero waste culture. The identification of the needs in the schools has permit to apply better the diversity of tools to promote preventions waste at schools.		
Description of the case study	<p>Use of teaching units and Apps created expressly for the project so that teachers can work with students to improve knowledge of how to separate waste.</p> <p>Some of the activities have made it in schools and others during summer camps. The activities involved.</p> <p>Project objective and material presentation with the school directives and teachers in charge of the project</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other_____	Waste fraction <input type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collection <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> On site treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other_____	Waste management stage <input type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies
Waste fraction	All waste		
Communication tools	Apps Digital projects Videos		

	Computer games
Training tools	Apps Computer games Separate bins Composting container
Other tools developed	Improve Knowledge of Prevention and Separate Collection
Rate of participation (% or number)	Depending on the activity carried out, 1 to 3 Zamudio schools were made with a participation rate of 100%
Environmental impact	Improve Knowledge of Prevention and Separate Collection
Social economical impact / benefit (forecasted and/or achieved, please specify)	<p>That the students take conscience of the environmental problematic that supposes the residues using also IT Tools.</p>
Information source	Waste4Think
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/ZAMUDIO/strategies/2

INTRODUCTION OF A SELF COMPOSTING IN THE SCHOOLS			
ID	Z2.2		
Municipality or Area	Zamudio		
Basic data	- Country: Zamudio, Basque Country, Spain - Population: 21.870 - Period of implementation: From 03/2018 to 11/2019 - Current status: Finished - Language(s): English		
Description of the case study	Use of composters by school students to understand and learn the process of composting giving value to organic waste by turning it into organic fertilizer for the school garden, that is a resource instead of garbage.		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign <input type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other_____	Waste fraction <input type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse Collection <input type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> On site treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other_____	Waste management stage <input type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies
Waste fraction	Self-composting		
Communication tools	Txorierrri community self-composting guide. (Txorierrri is the regional authority responsible of the management of the public service of the region which Zamudio belongs).		
Training tools	Sunflower game (digital compost container)		
N. of stakeholders involved	2 schools		
Rate of participation (% or number)	100%		

Key points of success	<p>It's a practical exercise and the students like it very much.</p> <p>If you explain the composting process well to the students, they are incredible managers.</p>
Environmental impact	<p>Reduce the amount of waste that is thrown into the street containers, reduce CO2 emissions and get a high quality organic fertilizer.</p>
Social economical impact / benefit	<p>Empower students in waste management. Save on the cost of treating organic waste.</p>
Costs detailed?	<p>2 Termometer: 27,8€ 2 Humidimetre: 41,8€ 2 Compost bin: 93,66€</p>
Monitoring methodology	<p>Measure temperature and humidity of the self-composting bins installed in the schools.</p>
Information source	<p>Waste4Think</p>
Link to the specific case study	<p>https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/ZAMUDIO/implementations/73</p>

CREATIVE COOKING COURSE			
ID	Z3.2		
Municipality or Area	Zamudio		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Zamudio, Basque Country, Spain</p> <p>- Population: 21.870</p> <p>- Period of implementation: From 02/2019 to 02/2019</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Description of the case study	<p>Students of the Vizcaya school prepared the recipe of Cod to the ajoarriero with vegetables with the leftovers of the previous days of fish and vegetables. It was the chef of the school who acted as a teacher in the cooking workshop and used the facilities of the cooking laboratory. And at all times was encouraged the importance of using leftover food and how much waste is not generated in this way.</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	<p>Type of campaign</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> All waste</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Glass</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Food waste</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Clothes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> All packaging</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other _____</p>	<p>Waste fraction</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Prevention</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Redesign</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reuse</p> <p>Collection</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Recycling</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Treatment</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> On site treatment</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other _____</p>	<p>Waste management stage</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Citizen</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Students</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> SME</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Researchers</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Associations</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies</p>
Waste fraction	Food waste		
N. of stakeholders involved	20 students		
Rate of participation (% or number)	100%		

<p>Key points of success</p>	<p>Students value food more when they cook it themselves.</p> <p>How much fun students have cooking and how much it affects them that so much food is wasted.</p>
<p>Environmental impact</p>	<p>Reduce Food waste generation.</p>
<p>Social economical impact / benefit</p>	<p>Teach students to take advantage of leftovers and to cook with leftovers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Promote relationships among students while they are cooking.X20. -Promote the circular economy. -That students learn to cook healthy things.
<p>Costs detailed?</p>	<p>There was no cost because the cook was from the Vizcaya school and the leftovers from the previous days of the dining room were cooked on the school premises.</p>
<p>Information source</p>	<p>Waste4Think</p>
<p>Link to the specific case study</p>	<p>https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/ZAMUDIO/implementations/123</p>

FOOD REDISTRIBUTION WITH REMAINS OF FOOD BETWEEN POOR FAMILIES			
ID	Z3.4		
Municipality or Area	Zamudio		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Zamudio, Basque Country, Spain</p> <p>- Population: 21.870</p> <p>- Period of implementation: From 03/2018, still in force</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Description of the case study	<p>Since last 1st of March, the solidary food storage container, will allow to collect surpluses from collective and professional kitchens of the local area to distribute them among a dozen families in the locality. The Vizcaya School participates in the donation of surpluses.</p> <p>Food deliveries will be weekly, and this will be delivered frozen and packed in a non-returnable pack, suitable for freezing and microwaves. The surplus of food will be subjected to a rigorous sanitary control. Also, the food will be frozen in containers with all the guarantees and will be delivered to the beneficiaries in isothermal bags in which there will be enough food for a week. These bags will be delivered at the beginning of the initiative, and the beneficiaries must carry them at the time of collection to ensure the maintenance of the cold chain.</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign <input type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	Waste fraction <input type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reuse Collection <input type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> On site treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	Waste management stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies
Waste fraction	Biowaste Edible food Foodwaste		

	Residual waste
Communication tools	<p>Http://www.deia.eus/2018/03/07/bizkaia/uribe-txorierrri/el-taper-solidario-llega-a-zamudio</p> <p>http://waste4think.eu/solidary-food-storage-container-arrives-zamudio</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sNjZLPf6gyw</p>
Training tools	AUNAR sources
N. of stakeholders involved	12 and then 21
Rate of participation (% or number)	200%
Key points of success	<p>AUNAR has a lot of background in this area and they have a well protocolized process.</p> <p>This action has not been enough time implemented to have main conclusions, but we would like to reach to more people.</p>
Environmental impact	<p>Reduce food waste and reduce residual waste that goes to the incinerator.</p> <p>Carbon footprint avoided.</p> <p>Water footprint avoided.</p>
Social economical impact / benefit	<p>A person who is at risk of social exclusion has a better balanced diet.</p> <p>Money saved thanks to the food wastage avoided.</p> <p>This action permits to increase the solidarity in the town and permits to make the problematic of the undernourishment of poor people of the village visible in a communitarian sense.</p>
Costs detailed?	There was no cost because the cook was from the Vizcaya school and the leftovers from the previous days of the dining room were cooked on the school premises.
Monitoring methodology	AUNAR annual report
Information source	Waste4Think and AUNAR Association
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/ZAMUDIO/implementations/4

TUPPER AND REUSABLE CAMPAIGN			
ID	Z4.2		
Municipality or Area	Zamudio		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Zamudio, Basque Country, Spain</p> <p>- Population: 21.870</p> <p>- Period of implementation: 2018-12-17 to 2019-01-31</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Description of the case study	<p>Not only the residual waste must be reduced, but also the lightweight packaging stream has a huge margin for reduction. Therefore, three main campaigns are going to be implemented in Zamudio through the commercial activities. Those need a Diagnosis to make a Tupper campaign.</p> <p>Reusable bags for local market are already running but it will be reinforced. In 2018 there was a joint campaign of tupperware and bags.</p> <p>And a Local Trade App campaign has also made it to support all those campaigns.</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign <input type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	Waste fraction <input type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reuse Collection <input type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> On site treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	Waste management stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies
Waste fraction	Light packaging		
Communication tools	<p>Local magazine.</p> <p>-Txorierri valley magazine.</p> <p>- El Correo Newspaper.</p>		

	- Explanation of the campaign given by the environmental educator when handing out the starter kit to the citizens.
Training tools	Experiences of similar campaigns in other municipalities.
N. of stakeholders involved	<p>Tupper Campaign</p> <p>Expected: 900</p> <p>Effective: 460</p>
Rate of participation (% or number)	51%
Key points of success	Talk to the merchants when preparing the campaign to find out the level of involvement of the stores. In this way we can know to what level they are willing to participate. In order for people to change their habits, the campaign has to be extended over time.
Environmental impact	Reduce the amount of plastic that reaches our natural ecosystems.
Social economical impact / benefit	<p>Raise public awareness of the problem of single-use plastics.</p> <p>Reduce costs to clean up our natural environments and get retailers to save on packaging to serve the purchase as they are reusable.</p>
Costs detailed?	<p>- Toppers: 2800 units = 3.974,124 €</p> <p>- Grates: 2800 units = 6.640,480 €</p> <p>- Isothermal bags: 1400 units= 2.541,000 €</p> <p>- Sandwich holder: 1400 units= 4.556,860 €</p> <p>- Nets for fruit: 5600 units= 8.266,720 €</p> <p>- Tickets: 12600 units= 411,400 €</p> <p>- Environmental educator hours= 524,7 €</p>
Monitoring methodology	<p>Surveys and participants number.</p> <p>Indicators:</p> <p>1. Reduction of light packaging: how much lightweight packaging have trades saved (€ or units).</p> <p>2. Real usage of the tupperware and reusable bags. How many people use it during the campaign and how much in the coming months (a comparative through a questionnaire)</p>

	to traders). 3. Business published in the Citizen App and app visits.
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/ZAMUDIO/strategies/4

CITIZENS PARTICIPATION PROCESS TO INTRODUCE PAYT AND DISCUSS WITH CITIZENS THE NEW TAX ASSOCIATED			
ID	Z6.2		
Municipality or Area	Zamudio		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Zamudio, Basque Country, Spain</p> <p>- Population: 21.870</p> <p>- Period of implementation: 2017 to 2018.</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Description of the case study	<p>Citizens participation process. When we made a survey and project presentation, municipality invite inhabitants to take part in the participation process. Those people, who want to take part, will be called to ensure their assistance. Municipality wants a heterogeneous participation group, so they will contact some people who probably are against the change. The first three meetings themes are defined: monitoring system and the location of containers, and the PAYT scheme (two). Municipality will hire an expert enterprise services (in participation process), which will be responsible of streamlining these meetings. These meetings will start with major' briefly presentation of the theme, and after that, we will start working in small groups. The meeting will finish putting the main conclusion in common and fulfilling a satisfaction survey. Enterprise must make a summary and share it with us, to distribute it among participators and inhabitants who want to know more about the process (uploading the summary on the website and publishing an article in local magazine).</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign	Waste fraction	Waste management stage
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packagin <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reuse Collection <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> On site treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies

Waste fraction	All waste
Communication tools	ZamudiOrain local magazine, calls/personal mailing to people who want to participate. AdiZamudio App
Training tools	Shadow invoicing
Other tools developed during the campaign	PAYT fiscal ordinance
N. of stakeholders involved	1st Workshop: effective: expected 20, effective 12 2nd workshop: expected 20 effective 12, 3thd workshop: expected 20, effective 14
Rate of participation (% or number)	60-70%
Key points of success	We hire a participation enterprise in order to make a more productive meeting. They prepare 2 dynamics, which were effective to let people participate. Weekday and hour was good.
Environmental impact	Increase knowledge of waste management.
Social economical impact / benefit	Empower citizens in important decisions of the municipality. In the end, a fairer rate will be achieved for all citizens.
Costs detailed?	1st meeting: 90€ 2ond meeting; 110 € 3td meeting: 95€
Monitoring methodology	After conclusions, the enterprise delivered to each citizen a survey asking about dynamic drivers, the workshop, the place and used materials.
Information source	Waste4Think
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/ZAMUDIO/strategies/6

DISTRIBUTION OF MENSTRUAL CUPS			
ID	Z9.4		
Municipality or Area	Zamudio		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Zamudio, Basque Country, Spain</p> <p>- Population: 21.870</p> <p>- Period of implementation: From 04/10/2018 to 16/10/2018.</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Description of the case study	<p>The workshop was about first menstruation and was aimed at young girls (9-12 years old) and their parents. In the 2 workshops of the first menstruation each of the girls who attended was given a reusable menstrual cup. Today it is still a little unknown to many people and there is some reluctance to use the cups by some people. And another important thing is that in this way we avoid generating sanitary textiles that should be thrown into the rest fraction.</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	<p>Type of campaign</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> All waste</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Glass</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Food waste</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Clothes</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Residual waste</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> All packagin</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other _____</p>	<p>Waste fraction</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Prevention</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Redesign</p> <p>Reuse</p> <p>Collection</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Recycling</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Treatment</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Onsite treatment</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other _____</p>	<p>Waste management stage</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Citizen</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Students</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> SME</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Researchers</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Associations</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Young girls and their parents</p>
Waste fraction	Residual Waste		
Communication tools	<p>"Announcement of the workshops on the first menstruation through the Zamudio town hall bulletin: http://www.zamudio.eus/es-ES/Recursos/Revista-Orain/Revista%20Orain/2018_urria_ZAMUDIORAIN77vWeb.pdf</p> <p>Http://farmaconfort.com/copas-menstruales/farmaconfort-copas-menstruales/"</p>		

N. of stakeholders involved	Expected: 35 Effective: 35	
Rate of participation (% or number)	100%	
Costs detailed?	537,30€ for 30 cups.	
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/ZAMUDIO/strategies/8	

EUSKAL ECOUNTER COMPETITION			
ID	Z9.5		
Municipality or Area	Zamudio		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Zamudio, Basque Country, Spain</p> <p>- Population: 21.870</p> <p>- Period of implementation: 25/07/2019 to 28/07/2019.</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Description of the case study	<p>In the frame of the Euskal Encounter 2019, which was this year especially addressed to environmental aspects, a Virtual Cities competition took place. 75 players organized in 20 teams have developed strategies to increase the circularity of their virtual cities by deciding the destination of their budgets and prioritizing among more than 30 projects.</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign	Waste fraction	Waste management stage
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packagin <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other_____	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse Collection <input type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> On site treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other_____	<input type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies
Waste fraction	All waste		
Communication tools	Euskal Ecounter Website: https://ee27.euskalencounter.org/en/opengune/talks.html Stand- banner- explanations of the "trainers"		
N. of stakeholders involved	Expected: 20 Effective: 75		
Rate of participation (% or number)	375%		

Key points of success	The activity was done in a context of various electronic games competitions that facilitated the interest of the players in participating.
Environmental impact	Increase knowledge of waste management.
Social economical impact / benefit	The students who participate in the competition learned about a multiplicity of criteria of circularity more over the most known
Costs detailed?	Stand: 1500€ Advertising banner: 120€ Prizes: 500€ 3 staff members dedicated to organize and prepare the initial presentation 2 days before the event 2 staff members during the 4 days event
Monitoring methodology	Qualitative survey results: Players see Virtual Cities as an interesting resource management game. The general opinion of the users was positive, they enjoyed the game and improved their knowledge about Circular Economy especially: - Understand that actions for the environment can not only be individual but can be raised within the framework of almost all systems of a city, and that they need budget, human resources and time to show the effects. - The game allows you to see how certain events and projects affect the city as a whole and how even if a project is good for circularity can diminish your social support. - To know some of the drivers of specific strategies of the Circular Economy like: - Reduce, Reuse, Recycling - Sustainable mobility - Ecological use of water - Sharing Economy - Energy and Buildings Players saw Virtual Cities as a very good educational tool that could be translated into several languages.
Information source	Waste4Think
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/ZAMUDIO/implementations/159

3.4 Halandri

ENVIRONMENTAL PROGRAM IN A VOCATIONAL SCHOOL			
ID	H1.1		
Municipality or Area	Halandri		
Basic data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Country: Halandri, Athens, Greece - Population: 73.970 - Period of implementation: from 2017 to 2019. Ongoing. - Language(s): English 		
Description of the case study	<p>Vocational School The municipality will organize a series of seminars and actions at high-schools (12-15 years old) directed at students. For 20-25 weeks, students will have a dedicated time around 1 ½ h, after school classes, to work on these issues. The learning materials will be used and also some other additional activities as real composting and sorting, visits to treatment plants, monitoring and characterization, etc. In the vocational school, they are going to work also on the biodiesel in a more technical point of view.</p> <p>The seminar talked about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activity about waste management - Waste Monitoring - Home Composting. - Visit Collection and plant. - Visit to food waste collection and plant. - Demonstration of Citizen Science action. - Recycling processes. - Waste Management/Monitoring (Recycling Indicators Measurements). - Defining the exact location of the school bins. - Educational briefing on waste sorting. - Implementation of STEAM Lesson 1 of Waste 4 Think. - Award ceremony. - Visit to food waste collection and plant. 		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign	Waste fraction	Waste management stage
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collection <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Onsite treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public

			<i>Bodies</i>
Waste fraction	All waste		
Communication tools	The main communication tool was across the channels of the school and her teacher.		
Training tools	Training tools: lessons in class and presentations, homework and individual research, activities at the schoolyard, use of simple measuring instruments (measuring tapes, scales, thermometers, hydrometers, pH-meters), a composter, paper forms, gloves, demonstrations and visits to the municipality's facilities and other relevant facilities.		
N. of stakeholders involved (expected and effective)	<p>It depends of the activity:</p> <p>Activity about waste management: expected: 32; effective: 32.</p> <p>Waste Monitoring: expected 32; effective 32.</p> <p>Home Composting: expected 32; effective: 32.</p> <p>Visit Collection and plant: expected 32, effective 32.</p> <p>Visit to food waste collection and plant expected 32, effective 32.</p> <p>Demonstration of Citizen Science action: expected: 32, effective 17.</p> <p>Recycling processes: expected 32, effective 32.</p> <p>Waste Management/Monitoring (Recycling Indicators Measurements): expected 40, effective 20.</p> <p>Defining the exact location of the school bins: expected: 40, effective: 20.</p> <p>Educational briefing on waste sorting: expected: 40, effective: 25.</p> <p>Implementation of STEAM Lesson 1 of Waste 4 Think: expected 40, effective 25.</p> <p>Award ceremony: expected 20, effective 20.</p> <p>Visit to food waste collection and plant: expected: 30, effective: 17.</p>		
Rate of participation (% or number)	50-100%		
Key points of success	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The teacher who has undertaken the task is very motivated and willing to take initiatives and push things. She also has a background in engineering, and so, is able to link both technical and educational goals. 2. The teacher has had experience in good waste management practices, so minimal training was required. 3. Budget for supporting educational actions is allocated in ENBIO's budget, so occasional funding for educational activities is possible without time consuming tendering processes. 4. The municipality's administration, ENBIO and NTUA have provided ample support to the school for its actions, and participated in morale-boosting actions (awards, school festivals, etc.). 5. The program has the support of the school's administration. <p>Lessons learned: The main difficulty in working with a vocational school is the fact that vocational schools traditionally attract students with lower expectations and educational ambitions. Sometimes, this is also reflected on the teachers. Environmental awareness is often low in such environments, and certain stereotypes become an obstacle, such as "people who deal with waste are garbage collectors". It is then an important step forward for us and a</p>		

	<p>testament to the teachers drive that the program has grown strong roots in the school.</p> <p>It must also be noted that students feel much more motivated when a lesson is followed by actions outside the classroom, especially when such an action is gamified, i.e. presented as a quest. Moreover, students respond well when their work is presented publicly and they are credited for it. Often, this was enough to ignore altogether stereotypical comments coming from their peers such the ones stated above.</p> <p>It is worth noting that the educational program in this school was not designed to be that ambitious. The initial planning was that one or two actions would take place, since we were initially focused in younger ages. However, the strong personal drive from the teacher of the school made it clear that more could be achieved, and thus we have an experience which we asses as highly replicable.</p> <p>STEAM Lessons Docs</p>
Social economical impact / benefit	The actions implemented, along with the support of the administration of the Municipality and the prestigious NTUA have helped to break stereotypes regarding waste management as a “lesser” work, thus enabling a greater reach to the students.
Costs related	Print maps: 10 €
Monitoring methodology	<p>Type: number of students, waste analysis at schools, composting results in all schools</p> <p>Means: scale, composting units with monitoring (temperature, moisture, etc.)</p> <p>Results indicators to be calculated</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Number of students involved 2. Usage of apps in the following weeks 3. Feedback from families <p>Other:</p> <p>Students use forms to register data they collect.</p> <p>Students are given homework’s and projects relevant to the specific actions.</p> <p>Waste generation, waste separated at source, compost produced.</p>
Information source	Waste4Think
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/HALANDRI/actions/57

USE OF THE ECODESIGN GAME			
ID	H2.2		
Municipality or Area	Halandri		
Basic data	<p>- Country: Halandri, Athens, Greece</p> <p>- Population: 73.970</p> <p>- Period of implementation: 2019</p> <p>- Current status: Finished</p> <p>- Language(s): English</p>		
Description of the case study	<p>Game to teach about how the decisions the industrial designers make at the beginning influences on the impact of the whole life cycle in terms of waste, energy, emissions, water and raw materials consumptions, etc.</p> <p>First phase: Ecodesign module introduction. Before using the Ecodesign game, a dedicated work will be done with the students of chemical engineering. They are going to work in groups working on ecodesign concept and developing specific projects applying what they have learned to some products and services. Some of the information developed will be used in the game.</p> <p>Second phase: Use of the Ecodesign game to teach about how the decisions the industrial designers make at the beginning influences on the impact of the whole life cycle in terms of waste, energy, emissions, water and raw materials consumptions, etc.</p>		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign	Waste fraction	Waste management stage
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Collection <input type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Onsite treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centers <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies
Waste fraction	All waste		

Communication tools	Smartphone, printed material
Key points of success	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Students understood that they should collaborate and include different skills and ideas in their efforts. 2. They combined their technical background with the principles of eco-design and life-cycle thinking introduced by the game. 3. Collaboration with Serious Games led to an improved version of the game. <p>Lessons learned: The most important lessons for the students were the necessity to collaborate and introduce different ideas in their designs and the importance of developing a full picture of the whole life-cycle (and the corresponding environmental impact of each stage) of the product</p>
Environmental impact	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Students familiarized themselves with the principles of eco-design. 2. Students learned things about life-cycle thinking.
Social, economic impact / benefit	<p>Students understood the importance of collaborating in diverse teams, when designing an innovative product.</p> <p>While playing the game students also considered financial aspects of product designing.</p>
Monitoring methodology	Feedback to Serious Games and improvements in the game mechanics.
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/HALANDRI/strategies/16

BIOWASTE SEPARATE COLLECTION IMPLEMENTATION	
ID	H3
Municipality or Area	Halandri
Basic data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Country: Halandri, Athens, Greece - Population: 73.970 - Period of implementation: from 2017 to 2019 - Current status: Finished - Language(s): English
Description of the case study	<p>Starting campaign. The municipality distributes the bins to the volunteer who will select the kitchen biowaste, solves doubts, enhance participation, etc. Pre-sorted biowaste collection will place every three days. In addition, the biowaste generated in open-air (fruit and vegetable) markets will be collected. Presorted food residues and market waste will be collected by a designated truck. The collected biowaste will be transferred to the waste management facility of the municipality, where will be dried and shredded to produce a biomass product (FORBI).</p> <p>In the week after the inaugural meeting, the 120 liters bins were deployed in spots that had been identified the previous days.</p> <p>At the same time, two routes were designed based on separating the municipality in two sectors and then calculating the optimal path for each route. The selection of the sectors was based on the expert opinion of the director of recycling of the municipality, and the paths were calculated by the company which provides the online monitoring and geolocating services for the municipality's waste management, based on their own optimal path implementation.</p> <p>A critical point was reached early in the deployment stage, as a significant amount of the 120 liters bins were stolen in the first 2 weeks. By the 10th day we had already 30 bins stolen. This alarming event could possibly endanger the survival of the project, since we knew that the early days would be critical for a solid adoption of good habits from the volunteers. We solved this problem by acquiring padlocks and using them to secure the bins in fixed spots, i.e. traffic signs, trees etc. Since then, we have had only rare occurrences of theft. However, we have reached the conclusion that 120lt bin is very easy to steal, and we should opt for larger 360 liters bins for future tenders.</p> <p>2nd stage: In November 2017 a waste analysis took place to a sample of about 5% of the participating households. All the three main waste streams were examined: commingled (green bin), recyclables (blue bin) and food waste (brown bin). We measured: a) the total amount per bin generated by our sample for 12 days, and b) the quality of the sorting. The results show that the population of participating households generate less and sort better than average, and confirm our initial assumptions that this population has much</p>

	better habits than the general population not only in sorting, but also in prevention.		
Waste fraction	Biowaste Edible food, Foodwaste, Residual waste		
Type(s) of campaign	Type of campaign <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All waste <input type="checkbox"/> Paper and cardboard <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Light packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Food waste <input type="checkbox"/> Goods and furniture <input type="checkbox"/> Clothes <input type="checkbox"/> Residual waste <input type="checkbox"/> All packaging <input type="checkbox"/> Bulky waste <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	Waste fraction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Redesign <input type="checkbox"/> Reuse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collection <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Onsite treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Preparation for reuse <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____	Waste management stage <input type="checkbox"/> Citizen <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Students <input type="checkbox"/> SME <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Associations <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Centres <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Non Residential Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Generator <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Collection Companies <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Plants Operators <input type="checkbox"/> Waste Manager Public Bodies
Waste fraction	All waste		
Communication tools	Website of Halandri https://www.chalandri.gr/yphresies/perivallon-aeiforia/waste4think/ (the site of the municipality has been redesigned recently and the old content has not yet been uploaded) E-mail, telephone contact, Facebook page.		
Key points of success	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The separate collection in the households is done in a way that minimizes the change in the daily routine, so it is easily adopted. 2. The households that have responded to the program seem to be more aware than the general public on waste management good habits Lessons learned: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. We find that collection twice a week is adequate and citizens are satisfied with it (i.e. acceptable odors). 2. Average consumption of biodegradable bags is 2-3 bags per week. 3. A lockable bin for collection seems to be necessary, since every bin that for some reason was left open (i.e. malfunctioning lock) was filled with impurities from improper use by non-participants. 4. The separate collection of the participants is very fastidious. It is possible that a more "relaxed" separate collection could enhance the amounts of organics collected, with insignificant change in the impurities. 		
Environmental impact	The impact is small to really matter at such a small scale (1% of the population), but the total amount of waste that can eventually be diverted from landfilling by using such a system totally changes the reuse and recycling rate of the rest of the blue (recyclables) and yellow (paper/cardboard) bin		

	system.
Social economical impact / benefit	<p>The presence of a small network of brown bins for kitchen biowaste creates curiosity among the citizens that notice them, and thus raise awareness of a new way of sorting household waste.</p> <p>The total amount of biowaste diverted from landfilling breaks even with the functional costs of the treatment, even at such a small scale pilot which cannot take advantage of economies of scale.</p>
Costs related	12.366 euros for bins, 600 euros for padlocks.
Monitoring methodology	<p>We monitor the participation of the citizens by using weighing sensors in the collection truck which are registered and are available on-line in real-time for each bin, and checking with a list of the participating households per bin.</p> <p>Waste analysis is done in a sample of bins of the participating households.</p>
Quality of the information found related to replicability of the campaign	<p>Number of households participating: 270</p> <p>Quantity collected of biowaste per capita and year: 73 kg/cap/year.</p> <p>% of impurities: 2%.</p> <p>Cost per ton of food waste collected: 140 €/t.</p>
Information source	Waste4Think
Link to the specific case study	https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/HALANDRI/strategies/17

4 Comments from external reviewers

4.1 External reviewer 1

DATE: 02/01/2020

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Has the document a Executive Summary?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	x		4	Some minor mistakes detected
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	x		5	
Glossary present in the document?	x		5	

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4.2 External reviewer 2

DATE: 21/01/2020

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Has the document a Executive Summary?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	x		4	Some minor mistakes detected
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	x		5	
Glossary present in the document?	x		5	

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4.3 External reviewer 3

DATE: 20/01/2020

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Has the document a Executive Summary?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	x		4	Some minor mistakes detected
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	x		5	
Glossary present in the document?	x		5	

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